

EFFICIENT DESIGN OF FAST FEATURE SUBSET SELECTION ALGORITHM FOR MULTI- DIMENSIONAL DATA BASED ON CLUSTERING

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Abstract

Feature selection for clustering of high dimensional data clustering is a difficult problem because of the broad number of redundant and irrelevant featured that the data can have that can run the clustering. A weighting scheme is proposed, wherein the weight for each feature is measured by its contribution to the given clustering task. Two different steps are proposed in the algorithm. In the first step features are divided into clusters using graph-theoretic clustering methods. In the second step, feature subsets are formed by the features that are strongly related to target classes. Feature subset selection research is focuses on searching for relevant features. The proposed logic on minimizes redundant data set and improves the feature subset accuracy. Efficient minimum-spanning tree (MST) clustering method to ensure efficiency of proposed algorithm, is adopted in the algorithm. Extensive experiments are carried out to compare the proposed algorithm and several other feature selection algorithms, namely, Relief, FCBF, CFS, Consist, and FOCUS-SF. The results, demonstrate that the algorithm not only produces smaller subsets of features but also improves the performances of the four types of classifiers.

Keywords- Feature subset selection, filter technique, feature clustering, graph-based clustering.

“I. EXISTING SYSTEM”

The embedded as a part of the training process incorporate feature selection and are usually specific to given learning algorithms. Thus they may be more efficient than the other three categories. Example of embedded approaches are traditional machine learning algorithms like decision trees or artificial neural networks. Predictive accuracy are used by wrapper methods learning algorithm to determine the goodness of the selected subsets. The accuracy of these learning algorithms is usually high. The computational complexity however is large and the generality of the selected features is limited. The filter methods don't dependent on learning algorithms and have good generality. Their computational complexity is low, with no guarantees about the accuracy of the learning algorithms is. The hybrid methods which are a combination of filter and wrapper methods use filter method to reduce search space and this will be considered by the wrapper subsequently. They focus on combining filter and wrapper methods in order to achieve the best possible performance when used with a particular learning algorithm and has similar time complexity of the filter methods.

A. DISADVANTAGES OF EXISTING SYSTEM:

- Lack of generality of the selected features .Large computational complexity is.
- Low computational complexity .No guarantee about the accuracy of the learning algorithms.

- The hybrid methods which are a combination of filter and wrapper methods use filter method to reduce search space which will be considered by the wrapper subsequently.

“II. PROPOSED SYSTEM”

Feature subset selection can be viewed as the process of identifying and removing as many irrelevant and redundant features as possible. This is because irrelevant features do not contribute to the predictive accuracy and redundant features do not redound to getting a better predictor for that they provide mostly information which is already present in other feature(s). Of the many feature subset selection algorithms, some can effectively eliminate irrelevant features but fail to handle redundant features yet some of others can eliminate the irrelevant while taking care of the redundant features. Our proposed FAST algorithm falls into the second group.

Keeping these in mind, we develop a novel algorithm which can efficiently and effectively deal with both irrelevant and redundant features, and obtain a good feature subset. We achieve this through a new feature selection framework (shown in Fig.1) which composed of the two connected components of irrelevant feature removal and redundant feature elimination. The former obtains features relevant to the target concept by eliminating irrelevant ones, and the latter removes redundant features from relevant ones via choosing representatives from different feature clusters, and thus produces the final subset. The irrelevant feature removal is straightforward once the right relevance measure is defined or selected, while the redundant feature elimination is a bit of sophisticated. In our proposed FAST algorithm , it involves (i) the construction of the minimum spanning tree (MST) from a weighted complete graph; (ii) the partitioning of the MST into a forest with each tree representing a cluster; and (iii) the selection of representative features from the clusters. The methodology used here is a five step methodology. The steps are data set management, finding symmetric uncertainty, irrelevant feature removal, minimum spanning tree construction and its clustering and the final step is target matching.

B.ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM:

- Low Time Consuming process
- Effective search is achieved based on feature search.
- There should be no outliers in the data.
- Easy to cluster the values.

The proposed system has mainly six modules namely Load Data and Classify, Information Gain Computation, TRelevance Calculation, Pearson Correlation calculation, MST Construction, Cluster Formation. The data has to be preprocessed for removing missing values, noise and outliers. Then the given dataset must be converted into the arff format which is the standard format for WEKA toolkit. From the arff format, only the attributes and the values are extracted and stored into the database.

Fig 1. Framework of the proposed system

C. Information Gain computation

Relevant features have strong correlation with target concept so are always necessary for a best subset, while redundant features are not because their values are completely correlated with each other. Thus, notions of feature redundancy and feature relevance are normally in terms of feature correlation and feature-target concept correlation. To find the relevance of each attribute with the class label, Information gain is computed. This is also said to be Mutual Information measure. Mutual information measures how much the distribution of the feature values and target classes differ from statistical independence. This is a nonlinear estimation of correlation between feature values or feature values and target classes.

$$IG(X|Y) = H(X) - H(X|Y)$$

To calculate gain, we need to find the entropy and conditional entropy values. The equations for that are given below:

$$H(X) = - \sum_i p(x_i) \log_2(p(x_i))$$

$$H(X|Y) = - \sum_{y \in Y} p(y) \sum_{x \in X} p(x|y) \log_2 p(x|y)$$

Where $p(x)$ is the probability density function and $p(x|y)$ is the conditional probability density function.

D. T-relevance calculation and F-Correlation

The relevance between the feature $F_i \in F$ and the target concept C is referred to as the T-Relevance of F_i and C , and denoted by $SU(F_i, C)$. If $SU(F_i, C)$ is greater than a predetermined threshold, we say that F_i is a strong T-Relevance feature.

$$SU(X, Y) = 2 \left[\frac{IG(X|Y)}{H(X) + H(Y)} \right]$$

After finding the relevance value, the redundant attributes will be removed with respect to the threshold value. The correlation between any pair of features F_i and F_j is called the F-Correlation of F_i and F_j , and denoted by $SU(F_i, F_j)$

E. Pearson Correlation calculation

Pearson Coefficient is used to measure the strength of a linear association between two variables, where the value $r = 1$ means a perfect positive correlation and the value $r = -1$ means a perfect negative correlation.

F. MST Construction

Kruskal's algorithm is a greedy algorithm in graph theory that finds a minimum spanning tree for a connected weighted graph. This means it finds a subset of the edges that forms a tree that includes every vertex, where the total weight of all the edges in the tree is minimized. If the graph is not connected, then it finds a minimum spanning forest (a minimum spanning tree for each connected component).

The description is as follows

1. Create a forest F (a set of trees), where each vertex in the graph is a separate tree.
2. Create a set S containing all the edges in the graph
3. While S is nonempty and F is not yet spanning
 - a. remove an edge with minimum weight from S
 - b. if that edge connects two different trees, then add it to the forest, combining two trees into a single tree
 - c. Otherwise discard that edge.

At the termination of the algorithm, the forest forms a minimum spanning forest of the graph. If the graph is connected, the forest has a single component and forms a minimum spanning tree.

Fig 2. Data Flow Diagram

“III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION”

The proposed FAST algorithm logically consists of three steps:

- (i) Remove irrelevant features,
- (ii) Constructs a MST from relative ones,
- (iii) Partitioning the MST and selects representative features

For the purposes of evaluating the performance and effectiveness of FAST algorithm, verifying whether or not the method is potentially useful in practice, and allowing other researchers to confirm our results, 35 publicly available data sets were used. The 35 data sets cover a range of application domains such as text, image and bio microarray data classification. A dataset file has been made in ASCII in CSV format, then conversion of this file to ARFF file is done. ARFF files are readable in Weka. The generated ARFF file is opened in Weka and then different processes like data cleaning, data processing and data transformation are applied on to the input database file. These steps act as preprocessing steps for the classification of data.

For a dataset D with m features and class C , T-Relevance is determined using the symmetrical uncertainty. Then Pearson correlation is used to reduce redundancy and construct a complete graph. The complete graph G reflects the correlations among all the target-relevant features. For high dimensional data, it is heavily dense and the edges with different weights are strongly interweaved.

Fig 3. System flow Diagram

Moreover, the decomposition of complete graph is NP-hard. Thus for graph G , construct a MST, which connects all vertices such that the sum of the weights of the edges is the minimum, using the well known Kruskal's algorithm. After building the MST, remove the edges, whose weights are smaller than both of the T-Relevance, from the MST and a Forest is obtained. Each tree in the Forest represents a cluster. Features in each cluster are redundant so choose

some more features apart from the representative with the help of fixing the threshold and comprise the final feature subset. (Figure 4) the below figure shows the user scenario diagram.

Fig 4. User Scenario Diagram

“IV. SYSTEM CONFIGURATION”

HARDWARE CONFIGURATION:-

- | | | |
|-------------|---|---------------------------|
| ✓ Processor | - | Pentium –IV |
| ✓ Speed | - | 2.1 Ghz |
| ✓ RAM | - | 2 GB(min) |
| ✓ Hard Disk | - | 160 GB |
| ✓ Key Board | - | Standard Windows Keyboard |
| ✓ Mouse | - | Two or Three Button Mouse |
| ✓ Monitor | - | SVGA |

SOFTWARE CONFIGURATION:-

- ✓ Operating System : Windows XP
- ✓ Programming Language : JAVA
- ✓ Java Version : JDK 1.6 & above.

“V. RESULT AND ANALYSIS”

When evaluating the performance of the feature subset selection algorithms, four metrics, 1) the proportion of selected features 2) the time to obtain the feature subset, 3) the classification accuracy, and 4) the Win/Draw/Loss record are used. The proportion of selected features is the ratio of the number of features selected by a feature selection algorithm to the original number of features of a dataset. The Win/Draw/Loss record presents three values on a given measure, i.e., the numbers of datasets for which our proposed algorithm FAST obtains better, equal, and worse performance than other five feature selection algorithms, respectively.

In the Existing System, there are so many clusters are formed based on the similar values. In this, we get accurate and small number of clusters. Through this, we can improve the efficiency by using Pearson coefficient.

“VI. CONCLUSION”

In this paper, novel clustering- based feature subset selection algorithm for high dimensional data is presented. The algorithm involves removing the irrelevant features, constructs the minimum spanning tree from relative ones, and partitioning the MST and selects representative features. In the proposed algorithm, a cluster based feature selection is done and thus dimensionality is drastically reduced. For efficiency Pearson correlation is used for removing the redundant data. For the future work, we plan to explore different types of correlation measures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

In performing our research, we had to take the help and guideline of some respected persons, who deserve our greatest gratitude. The completion of this assignment gives us much Pleasure. We would like to show our gratitude to our Mr. Dr K Raghuv eer Head of the Department, Information Science and Engineering, The National Institute Of Engineering, Mysore for giving us a good guideline for assignment throughout numerous consultations. We would also like to expand our deepest gratitude to all those who have directly and indirectly guided us in writing this research paper.

In addition, a thank you to C N Chinnaswamy, Assnt Professor, Information Science The National Institute Of Engineering, Mysore who introduced us to the Methodology of work, and whose passion for the “Data mining” had lasting effect.

Many people, especially our classmates and team members itself, have made valuable comment suggestions on this proposal which gave us an inspiration to improve our project. We thank all the people for their help directly and indirectly to complete our work.

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